

Mechanism of Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Bromamine-T and Hypobromite Ion in Alkaline Medium. A Kinetic Study

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Manuscript received 17 June 1986, revised 8 October 1987, accepted 27 January 1988

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by bromamine-T (BAT) and hypobromite ion have been investigated in alkaline medium. The rate followed first order kinetics in [oxidant] with both BAT and OBr^- , but fractional and inverse fractional orders in $[\text{OH}^-]$ with BAT and OBr^- , respectively. The rate was independent of $[\text{NCS}^-]$ with BAT and small fractional order in $[\text{NCS}^-]$ with OBr^- . Increase in ionic strength of the medium increased the rate with BAT and had no effect in hypobromite oxidations. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition with methanol increased the rate with BAT and had no significant effect with OBr^- oxidation. Activation parameters have been computed from the Arrhenius plots. Mechanisms consistent with the observed kinetics have been proposed and the related rate laws deduced. The formation equilibrium constant and the rate constant for the rate-controlling step have been computed from the double reciprocal plots. Comparison of kinetic results in acid and alkaline media reveal that BAT is more powerful oxidant in alkaline medium than in the former.

As a part of our mechanistic investigations of thiocyanate reactions¹⁻⁵ we report herein kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by bromamine-T (BAT) and hypobromite ion in alkaline medium. The thiocyanate reactions are of interest both from theoretical and industrial view points, and also of analytical, medicinal and biological importance. The kinetics of thiocyanate reactions studied so far include oxidation by hydrogen peroxide⁶, iodine⁷, Cr^{VI} , V^{V} ⁸, Bi^{V} ⁹, and some of the aromatic halo-sulphonamides¹⁻⁵.

Experimental

Bromamine-T was prepared by the partial debromination of dibromamine-T in NaOH solution (4.0 mol dm^{-3})¹⁰. Purity of the oxidant was checked by elemental analysis and its ir and nmr spectra, and was further confirmed by the iodometric estimation of active bromine present. An aqueous stock solution ($\sim 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of the oxidant was standardised and stored in dark-coloured bottles. Sodium hypobromite solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) was prepared by the standard method. Potassium thiocyanate (A.R.) was dried at 150° and its aqueous stock solution ($\sim 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was standardised by argentometric method. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Ionic strength of the reaction media was maintained at 0.5 mol dm^{-3} using concentrated aqueous NaClO_4 solution.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic runs were made in glass-stoppered pyrex tubes whose outer

surfaces were coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions with $[\text{NCS}^-]$ always greater than [oxidant] at least by 5-10 times. The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition of the measured amount of oxidant solution, thermostated at the desired temperature, to a solution containing known amounts of thiocyanate, sodium hydroxide and sodium perchlorate in the tube, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed by the least-square method were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of thiocyanate-BAT/ OBr^- reactions was determined under both substrate-excess and oxidant-excess conditions at different $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($0.001 - 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) by equilibrating varying ratios of $[\text{NCS}^-]/[\text{oxidant}]$ for 24 h at 303 K. Sulphate among the reaction products was detected by the conventional tests¹¹ and estimated by gravimetric method¹², the yields being $95 \pm 3\%$. Further, cyanogen bromide was quantitatively estimated by the iodometric method¹³. CNBr in the reaction products was treated with H_2SO_4 and 10% KI solution. The iodine liberated by the reaction, $\text{CNBr} + 2\text{KI} \rightarrow \text{KBr} + \text{KCN} + \text{I}_2$, was titrated against sodium thiosulphate (0.01 mol dm^{-3}); a $94 \pm 3\%$ yield of CNBr was obtained. *p*-Toluenesulphonamide (PTS), the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by paper chromatography with benzyl

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TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY BROMAMINE-T AND HYPOBROMITE ION IN ALKALINE MEDIUM

Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[X](mol dm ⁻³)				[X](mol dm ⁻³)			
$\times 10^3$ [BAT]	$\times 10$ [NCS ⁻]	$\times 10^3$ [OH ⁻]	$\times 10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^3$ [OBr ⁻]	$\times 10$ [NCS ⁻]	$\times 10$ [OH ⁻]	$\times 10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹
0.5	1.0	2.5	10.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.1
1.0	1.0	2.5	10.3	0.75	0.5	1.0	6.8
2.0	1.0	2.5	10.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	6.8
5.0	1.0	2.5	10.5	2.0	0.5	1.0	6.8
7.5	1.0	2.5	10.1	3.0	0.5	1.0	6.7
10.0	1.0	2.5	10.8	1.0	0.1	1.0	5.6
5.0	0.2	2.5	10.5	1.0	0.2	1.0	6.2
5.0	0.5	2.5	10.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	6.8
5.0	1.0	2.5	10.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	7.1
5.0	2.5	2.5	10.5	1.0	2.0	1.0	7.8
5.0	5.0	2.5	10.5	1.0	0.5	0.1	16.6
5.0	1.0	0.5	5.4	1.0	0.5	0.2	19.3
5.0	1.0	1.0	6.9	1.0	0.5	0.5	8.9
5.0	1.0	2.5	10.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	6.8
5.0	1.0	5.0	14.1	1.0	0.5	1.5	5.6
5.0	1.0	10.0	18.2	1.0	0.5	2.0	5.2

alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent ($R_f = 0.91$). The observed stoichiometries may be represented by equations (1) and (2),

where, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$.

Results

Kinetics of BAT oxidations: Kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by BAT in alkaline medium were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants and alkali (Tables 1–3). The plots of $\log [\text{BAT}]_0/[\text{BAT}]$ vs time were linear at least upto 65% completion of the reaction at both low and high substrate concentrations. But at low $[\text{NCS}^-]$ (upto 0.02 mol dm^{-3}), pseudo-first order constants decreased with the increase in $[\text{BAT}]^{1.4}$. Zero and half order plots in oxidant were also found to be non-linear. At high substrate concentrations ($> 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), the pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the change in $[\text{BAT}]$ showing first order kinetics in $[\text{BAT}]$ (Table 1). At high $[\text{NCS}^-]$, the rate was unaffected by the change in its concentrations ($0.02-0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The rate increased with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ with a fractional order of about 0.4 (Tables 1 and 3). Addition of the reaction products PTS and Br^- had no effect on the rate (Table 2). But the rate increased with either increase in ionic strength or decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition with methanol (Table 2).

Kinetics of hypobromite oxidations: The plots of $\log [\text{OBr}^-]_0/[\text{OBr}^-]$ vs time were linear for at least two half-lives and the pseudo-first-order rate

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATIONS OF IONIC STRENGTH, DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF MEDIUM AND REACTION PRODUCTS ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY BROMAMINE-T AND HYPOBROMITE ION

Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (except during its variation)

μ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)		Methanol %	$\times 10^4 k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)	
	BAT*	NaOBr**		BAT*	NaOBr**
0.021	—	6.7	0	10.5	6.8
0.13	7.7	6.7	5	20.8	7.1
0.20	8.2	—	10	39.5	7.2
0.50	10.5	6.8	20	63.9	7.2
1.0	11.5	6.8	—	—	—
$\times 10^3$ [KBr] (mol dm ⁻³)					
0	10.5	6.5*			
0.5	10.5	—			
1.0	10.5	6.8			
5.0	10.5	6.8			
10.0	—	6.9			
100.0	—	7.1			

* 10^3 [BAT] = 5.0 mol dm⁻³; 10 [NCS⁻] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
 10^3 [OH⁻] = 2.5 mol dm⁻³; ** 10^3 [NaOBr] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
 10 [NCS⁻] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³; 10 [OH⁻] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³.

TABLE 3—OBSERVED ORDERS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY BROMAMINE-T AND HYPOBROMITE*

Orders observed in	BAT	NaOBr
[Ox]	1 (1)	1 (1)
[NCS ⁻]	0 (0.3)	0.1 (0.97)
[OH ⁻] ([H ⁺])	0.4 (0.34)	-0.4 (2.0)
log A	6.14	6.73
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	52.9	57.4
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	50.4	54.9
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	59.6	63.3
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-30.5	-27.8

*Values in parantheses are kinetic parameters for oxidation in acid medium.

constants were insensitive to the changes in $[\text{OBr}^-]_0$ (Table 1) establishing first order kinetics in $[\text{OBr}^-]$.

The rate increased with the increase in $[\text{NCS}^-]$ ($0.01-0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with a little fractional order kinetics in $[\text{NCS}^-]$. The rate decreased with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($0.01-0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with an inverse fractional order in $[\text{OH}^-]$. Addition of one of the reaction products, Br^- , or variation in ionic strength or dielectric constant of the reaction medium had no significant effect on the rate of oxidation.

Activation parameters have been computed, in both the oxidations, from the Arrhenius plots, $\log k$ vs $1/T$ and $\log(k/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Table 3).

Discussion

Mechanism of oxidations :

Bromamine-T-NCS⁻ reaction : Bromamine-T (RNBrNa) is analogous to chloramine-T^{4,15,16} and bromamine-B¹⁷. It is moderately a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions and dissociates into RNBr^- and Na^+ . Monobromamine-T (RNHBr) formed in acid solutions undergoes disproportionation to dibromamine-T ($2\text{RNHBr} \rightleftharpoons \text{RNH}_2 + \text{RNBr}_2$) and hydrolyses to hypobromous acid, ($\text{RNHBr} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{HOBr} + \text{RNH}_2$). The latter gives hypobromite ion ($\text{HOBr} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{OBr}^-$; $K_a = 2.0 \times 10^{-9}$ at 298 K) in the alkaline solutions. Hence the probable oxidising species in alkaline aqueous solutions of BAT are RNBr^- , RNHBr , HOBr and OBr^- .

The kinetics of first order in $[\text{BAT}]$, zero order in $[\text{NCS}^-]$ and fractional order in $[\text{OH}^-]$ and the observed non-influence of the reaction products and increase of rate with ionic strength of the medium may be explained in Scheme 1.

Application of steady state treatment to the intermediate $[\text{X}]$ leads to the rate laws (3) and (4),

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{BAT}]_0 [\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1 [\text{OH}^-]}$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1 [\text{OH}^-]} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{K_1 k_2 [\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (4)$$

The linear plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{OH}^-]$ is in conformity with rate law (4) (Fig. 2). The formation constant (K_1) and disproportionation constant (k_2) were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot ($k_2 = 3.95 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $K_1 = 2314.1$). Scheme 1 depicts the decomposition of BAT to HOBr which

in turn reacts very rapidly with NCS^- in steps independent of $[\text{NCS}^-]$. This has been verified independently by investigating the kinetics of oxidation of NCS^- by hypobromite ion under similar conditions (Tables 1 and 3). As can be seen, the rate of oxidation of NCS^- by hypobromite is almost independent of $[\text{NCS}^-]$. These investigations provide additional support to the proposed mechanism.

Hypobromite-NCS⁻ reaction : The observed kinetics of first order in $[\text{OBr}^-]$, a little fractional order in $[\text{NCS}^-]$ and inverse fractional order in $[\text{OH}^-]$ can be accounted by Scheme 2.

Based on Scheme 2, rate law (5) has been deduced,

$$-\frac{d[\text{OBr}^-]}{dt} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [\text{OBr}^-]_0 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_4 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (5)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_4 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (6)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{K_4 k_5 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} + \frac{1}{k_5} \quad (7)$$

Rate law (7) predicts linearity between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ or $1/[\text{NCS}^-]$. The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{NCS}^-]$ (Figs. 1 and 2) are linear with finite intercepts in conformity with rate law (7).

Fig. 1. Plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{NCS}^-]$ at different temperatures, $10^4[\text{NaOBr}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4[\text{OH}^-] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

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